

**THE METHOD OF FORMING THE LEGAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS IN
LEGAL TECHNICAL SCHOOLS**

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***Abstract.** This article presents proposals and recommendations on methods of formation of legal competence of students in legal technical schools.*

***Key words:** law, competence, technical school, credit module, resource, college, pedagogical activity.*

Based on the systematic formation of a database describing the quality of education, the level of pedagogical activity, educational and methodological work, the knowledge of students and graduates in legal technical schools, and their assessment according to the rating indicators, an annually updated ranking of legal technical schools was organized. Current, intermediate and final types of control are conducted in the legal technical school to ensure that the level of knowledge and mastery of students is in accordance with the state educational standards. Academic mobility is ensured by the fact that the students of the legal technical school go to the legal technical school in the territory of the republic or to another educational institution in a foreign country for a certain period of time. "Also, according to the results of education, the unit of measurement of the learning load mastered by the student in a particular subject is determined - credit. In order to ensure the academic mobility of students, transfer and recognition of credits received in the educational program of one educational institution to another educational institution is carried out on the basis of credit transfer. Accumulation of credit units, which are provided as a result of mastering educational elements and achieving other achievements, is achieved as a result of credit accumulation" [1, 2].

It is known that a set of documents consisting of educational standards, curriculum, educational subjects (modules) programs, qualification practice programs, which determine the main content of professional training aimed at enabling a graduate of a legal technical school to competently perform professional activities in a specific specialty, is called an educational program.

During the research period, we studied information about the description of the legal technical school, access to the credit module system, available educational specialties, services and resources, programs of academic subjects, and the description of the elements of specific educational programs as a catalog of educational programs. As a result of our studies, an information system for managing the educational process in legal technical schools was established, according to it, an electronic system with the capabilities of registering students, distributing educational materials, ensuring mutual cooperation between students and teaching staff, assigning tasks, conducting inspections, evaluating and recording its results. is available.

In legal technical schools, a separate academic module has been introduced, which covers knowledge and professional aspects, and ends with an appropriate type of supervision as a structural element of the educational program aimed at forming knowledge, skills and competences. The modules mastered, the amount of credits earned, and the grades obtained are reflected in the student's certificate of academic achievement.

Educational elements in legal technical schools are a part of the educational program and are a type of training that helps to achieve educational results and master the knowledge specified in the educational program.

According to our observations, there are still some unresolved conflicting problems in

the educational processes of legal technical schools. For example, directions that determine the student's personal learning trajectory, chosen by the student and giving him the opportunity to sequentially accumulate knowledge and acquire the desired set of competencies, are still reflected only on paper. Also, while the educational trajectory of a technical school student is created with the help of institutional documents and guidelines, it is not intended to obtain the same qualification as a result of different educational trajectories. "We should note that all this is reflected in determining the amount of time necessary to achieve the expected educational results based on the implementation of all types of educational activities (lecture, practical training, seminar, practice and independent work)" [2] .

In order to improve the quality of education in legal technical schools and to create competition among teaching staff, despite the fact that through the portal of the educational process management information system, students are given the opportunity to choose teaching staff in the process of forming their personal educational trajectory within the module, in some technical schools, due to the lack of widespread involvement of specialists, there is a weakness in this work.

Another of the still unresolved conflicting issues in the educational processes of legal technical schools is that although detailed information about the educational program catalog and teaching conditions is uploaded and published on the official website of legal technical schools, it can be pointed out that in some technical schools (Navoi, Samarkand) they are not updated.

When analyzing the educational process in legal technical schools, it can be seen that the educational process is planned on the basis of a student-oriented approach in the form of dialogue between students, teaching staff and the administration, however, the wishes and desires of students are discussed in this process, and all interested parties are involved in the constructive discussion of the creation and implementation of the educational program. It can be seen that the participation of student representatives in the discussions through the right to vote is weak. Also, although the student is allowed to choose additional educational modules, the list of which is provided, or to choose an additional subject from the list of subjects available in the elective subjects of the curriculum of another educational field, on the basis of a fee-contract, it was found that there is laxity in this regard in some technical schools.

In order to resolve these conflicting aspects revealed by our observations, we developed the following recommendations: taking into account the fact that the educational process in legal technical schools consists of educational and control (module knowledge acquisition and evaluation of their results) activities, in the planning of the educational process, the catalog of the educational program and the curriculum, in the development of the curriculum (syllabus) of the modules, it is desirable to widely involve the leading educational institutions of our republic and foreign experts, and at the same time to form the personal educational trajectory of students in accordance with the curriculum and the list of elective subjects: it is advisable to involve qualified specialists in drawing up the schedule of the educational process, the schedule of training sessions for academic groups, and to include in the curriculum elements of education in which additional credits are allocated to be acquired voluntarily by students.

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